

MODERN LANGUAGE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the use of modern technologies of teaching foreign language in high school. The problem of intensification of teaching foreign languages has been considered, modern methods and training technologies have been characterized, guidelines on the use of various methods and techniques have been offered depending on the purpose, content and stage of learning a foreign language in high school.

Keywords: web site, web page, interactive, Internet, Internet technologies, casetechnology, computer technology, the method projects, training in collaboration, educational technology, language portfolio.

The term learning technologies (or pedagogical technologies) is used to refer to a set of teacher's work methods (methods of his scientific organization of work), with the help of which the learning goals set in the lesson are achieved with the greatest efficiency in the shortest possible period of time to achieve them. The term was widely used in the literature of the 60s. XX century in connection with the development of programmed learning and was originally used to refer to learning using technical means. In the 70s. the term has become more widely used: both to refer to learning using TCO and as a rationally organized learning in general. Thus, the concept of "learning technologies" began to include all the main problems of didactics related to improving the educational process and increasing the efficiency and quality of its organization.

Nowadays, there has been a differentiation of two components of the content of the term: technology of teaching (Technology of Teaching) and technology in teaching (Technology in Teaching). With the help of the first term, the methods of the scientific organization of the teacher's work are denoted, with the help of which the set learning goals are best achieved, and with the help of the second, the use of technical teaching aids in the educational process. The most important characteristics of learning technologies are the following:

- ❖ *effectiveness (high level of achievement of the set educational goal by each student);*
- ❖ *cost-effectiveness (a large amount of educational material is assimilated per unit of time with the least effort spent on mastering the material);*

- ❖ *ergonomics (learning takes place in an atmosphere of cooperation, a positive emotional microclimate, in the absence of overload and overwork);*
- ❖ *high motivation in studying the subject, which contributes to an increase in interest in classes and allows you to improve the best personal qualities of the student, to reveal his reserve capabilities.*

Most researchers consider learning technologies as one of the ways to implement a personal-activity approach to learning in the classroom, thanks to which students act as active creative subjects of learning activities. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, it is customary to refer to modern learning technologies: learning in collaboration, the project method (project technologies), student-centered learning, distance learning, the use of a language portfolio, computer and audiovisual technologies.

Consider some of the listed learning technologies.

Collaborative learning. This technology is based on the idea of interaction between students in a group of classes, the idea of mutual learning, in which students take not only individual but also collective responsibility for solving learning problems, help each other and bear collective responsibility for the success of each student. Unlike frontal and individual learning, in which the student acts as an individual subject of educational activity, is responsible only "for himself", for his successes and failures, and the relationship with the teacher is subject-subjective in nature, when learning in cooperation, conditions for interaction are created. and cooperation in the system "student - teacher - group" and the actualization of the collective subject of educational activity takes place. Together, the task is solved, and strong students help the weaker ones in the success of its implementation. This is the general idea of collaborative learning, and to complete the learning task, the study group is formed in such a way that it has both strong and weak students. The assessment for the completed task is put one per group.

Computer training. This is teaching a foreign language using curricula designed to work with a computer. It arose on the ideas of programmed learning and today has a significant impact on all aspects of the educational process in connection with the mass computerization of secondary and higher schools, the creation of computer programs for academic disciplines, including for those who study foreign languages, the use of the Internet, as classes, as well as in the independent work of students.

Computer linguodidactics is an interdisciplinary field of knowledge and closely interacts with the development of information technology, applied and

mathematical linguistics, developments in the field of artificial intelligence, computer program design, research on human-computer interaction, theory and practice of computer learning in general. This discipline has been formed as an independent direction in the teaching of languages since the late 80s of the XX century and three areas of research have been developed in it:

- 1) development of theoretical aspects of the use of computers in language teaching (methodological problems of computer linguodidactics, typology of computer educational materials, evaluation of the effectiveness of computer teaching aids, etc.);
- 2) experimental work on the creation and use in the educational process of computer materials for various purposes, stages and profiles of language teaching;
- 3) ways to integrate computer learning into the overall process of language learning.

Since the mid-80s of the last century, special terms have been used to define the field of theory and practice of using computers in language teaching, including: "Computer Assisted Language Learning" (CALL) - learning a language using a computer and "Computer Aided Language Instruction" (CALI) - computer-assisted language learning. Nowadays, due to the widespread use of computer technology, the term "Information and Communication Technologies" - "information and communication technologies" has also become widespread. At the same time, the term CALL - Computer Assisted Language Learning - retains its meaning as a general term for the whole complex of theoretical and applied problems associated with computer language learning. In domestic linguodidactics, the term "Computer linguodidactics", proposed in 1991 by K.R. Piotrovskaya and developed in relation to teaching languages.

Computer training programs for students of foreign languages are issued in the form of electronic textbooks, the characteristic features of which are:

- *the presence of a software module (video clips, voiced dialogues, a dictionary), a training module (a set of exercises of a language and speech nature), a module for recording and reproducing speech;*
- *presentation of educational material in visual and audio form;*
- *the organization of the material in the form of hypertext, which allows you to quickly move from one section of the manual to another, to search for information;*
- *the ability, when performing control tasks, to compare your answer with the standard stored in the data bank, and get a grade for your answer.*

Some courses have Internet support in the form of additional training materials, methodological recommendations, which are accessed via computer networks. At present, the following types of computer training programs have become widespread: those devoted to mastering individual sections of the language system; the formation of speech skills; control programs that assess the level of language proficiency; sociocultural programs that introduce the culture of the country of the language being studied. Unfortunately, there is not yet a sufficient number of programs that teach speech communication. At the same time, in the programs of recent years, multimedia systems have been increasingly used that synthesize sound, video and text, which makes it possible to use all types and visual aids with maximum efficiency within the framework of a computer training course. With the advent and development of the Internet, the possibilities of using computers in teaching a foreign language have expanded enormously.

Three main activities of students in the global network are considered:

- 1) Activities aimed at the perception of information in the form of texts, electronic newspapers, books, audio and video broadcasts. Checking the effectiveness of perception is carried out in this case in the traditional way, as well as when working with ordinary printed text, audio and video recordings.
- 2) Active activity, when the student, along with the perception of information, participates in filling out online forms, performs tests, the results of which are instantly evaluated and displayed on the screen, sends e-mails and postcards, creates his own web pages, participates in joint online projects, plays online games, etc.
- 3) Interactive activity, when a student is both a sender and a recipient of information.

These are different types of chats, i.e. real-time conversations, audio and video conferences, distance learning sessions. If the organization of the last two types of activity requires certain technical parameters, and, above all, the possibility of accessing the Internet during a lesson at a sufficiently high data exchange rate, then extracting information from the Internet as a type of independent work outside of school hours can and should be widely used in everyday life. teaching practice. The use of Internet technologies allows the teacher to model alternative learning strategies that take into account the psychological characteristics of students. Only a computer makes it possible to effectively combine auditory, visual and kinesthetic learning styles. The creation of the Internet has opened up truly unlimited possibilities for filling foreign language

teaching with modern authentic content. The latest editions of world-famous newspapers, breaking news videos, correspondence, online discussions with native speakers - ten years ago one could only dream of this.

Teaching professionally oriented communication using this technology requires both the teacher and students to possess a number of well-formed professional communication skills. *These include:*

- ✓ *the ability to perceive and evaluate information received in verbal and non-verbal form;*
- ✓ *the ability to diagnose and analyze the problem;*
- ✓ *the ability to formulate and logically build a statement in compliance with the norms of the language;*
- ✓ *the ability to take part in the discussion;*
- ✓ *the ability to participate in the adoption of a collective decision.*

The formation of professional skills to teach business communication using the "case stage" technology should begin with simple situations of small volume that are of interest to the entire group of students. Its goal is to develop teamwork skills through joint discussion of the case situation. The topic of the situation gives each student the opportunity to express their opinion and take part in the development of a joint decision that will be submitted for discussion. Having become acquainted with the content of the case, students are invited to express their opinion, first in the form of a monologue, and then take part in the discussion (dialogue form of communication), during which the optimal solution should be found. Thus, modern technologies for teaching foreign languages allow us to conclude that at present there are two main ways to intensify the learning process: one - through the maximum use of technical means, the other - through the activation of the reserves of the personality of each student. It can be argued that the development of intensive methods, which provide for the organic inclusion of technical means in the training system, will be the most promising direction for improving the methodology in the coming years in the direction of intensifying the educational process. There is no doubt that the most promising for the coming years will be learning technologies that involve the use of computers and various forms of distance learning in the educational process.

References:

1. Azimov E.G., Samuylova N.I., Shamshi L.B. TSO at the present stage of development of the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language // Russian Language Abroad. 1998. No. 2.

2. Kharatova, S. (2022, November). The role of integrated education in teaching foreign languages. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 1, No. 31, pp. 4-6).
3. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.
4. Харатова, Ш. Х., & Садикова, М. Б. (2020). Эффективные способы изучения английского языка. *Academy*, (2 (53)), 33-35.
5. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Tendencies of development of distance education in global transformation. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 353-362.
6. Kharatova, S. K. Goals And Tasks Of English Language Teaching. *International Bulletin Of Engineering And Technology*, 2(9).
7. Botvenko M.A. Computer linguodidactics: textbook. allowance. M., 2005. 112 p.

